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Council Library Resources, Inc.
on

39th Annual Report, 1995

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Acknowledgments

The W. K. Kellogg Foundation and the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation provided support for Council programs during 1993/1994. We appreciate their support for our efforts on behalf of libraries and information services and their users.

1. Through November 8, 1994.
2. Elected November 8, 1994.
3. Retired November 8, 1994.
4. As of January 1, 1995.
5. Resigned, December 31, 1994.
6. As of November 8, 1994

7. Until November 8, 1994
8. Elected April 25, 1995
9. Through April 25, 1995
10. Served May 1–June 30, 1995
11. Through March 31, 1995
12. As of April 3, 1995

Chairman's Message

We have entered a period of rapid change in the leadership and program direction for the Council on Library Resources. The appointment of Deanna Marcum as President in January 1995 has led to a re-examination of the Council's goals and objectives—as well as a streamlining of its management and administrative services.

The Board of Directors has accepted with enthusiasm the new President's plan to concentrate its program on activities related to: 1) the development of leadership in libraries to manage better the transformation resulting from the application of new technologies for improved services and products; 2) the transition to the electronic library, including serving as a special source of information for planning and implementing coherent links among such libraries; and, 3) the economics of information, with special reference to understanding better the costs of hardware, software, databases, and the related costs of maintaining new electronic information systems.

During the past year, the Council engaged in a major project supported by the W. K. Kellogg Foundation. The goal is to foster the development of leadership within the library and information science community to create a society of well-informed problem solvers. CLR has begun to work with several important educational and library organizations to develop plans and disseminate information to achieve this purpose.

The Council has also undertaken an important study of the costs of interlibrary lending and borrowing. The study is being performed in collaboration with the Association of Research Libraries, which has extensive experience in this field. The aim of this research is

to identify the characteristics of those libraries that are able to provide lending services more economically and efficiently than other libraries or comparable institutions. The study will also analyze the great variations in the costs of borrowing. A reduction in the costs of interlibrary lending may lead to an annual savings of millions of dollars.

In April 1995, the Board agreed to release Dr. Marcum on a half-time basis so that she could accept an offer to serve concurrently as president of the Commission on Preservation and Access. The Board also agreed to affiliate with the Commission because the missions and activities of the two organizations have become increasingly more complementary as advances in technology related to information gathering, storage, and access have created new challenges and opportunities for libraries. The principles of affiliation were defined as follows:

1. The missions of the Council and Commission will remain distinct but complementary.
2. The independence and responsibility of the separate Boards of Directors will be preserved.
3. The Council and Commission will retain financial independence and responsibility.
4. The Council and Commission may undertake cooperative projects when so approved by both Boards of Directors.
5. The Council and Commission will have a common president and a common treasurer.
6. The president of the Council and Commission is authorized, empowered, and

directed to implement, or cause to be implemented, such affiliation through all means deemed advisable, including, but not limited to, reorganizing the daily operations of the Council and Commission by consolidating employees and programmatic assignments, provided that the president shall make periodic reports to both Boards of Directors regarding the implementation of such affiliation.

This arrangement has made it possible to share administrative costs and to reduce the size and cost of office space and staff. It is hoped that the co-presidency will lead to cooperative program activities in support of our common library and user communities. These new administrative arrangements have been endorsed by our principal sponsors, the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and the W. K. Kellogg Foundation, as well as by the major library associations and other interested agencies.

The Chairman is particularly indebted to the vice-chair, Dr. William Hubbard; past-president, Maximilian Kempner; and members of the Executive Committee (Marilyn Gell-Mason, Jerry Campbell, and Daniel Tonkery), who were exceptionally helpful in our search for a new president and in all the discussions and negotiations leading to our administrative arrangements with the Commission on Preservation and Access. Board members remain committed to fulfilling the Council's mission of identifying and helping solve problems affecting library operations and bringing about achievements that are beneficial to the scholars, educators, and students who are engaged in our nation's research and educational enterprises.

Martin M. Cummings

President's M e s s a g e

The 39th anniversary of the Council on Library Resources will occur on September 16, 1995. Individuals facing their fortieth birthday often have difficulty coming to terms with the pattern and texture of middle-age; so it is with the Council. Established as a special-focus foundation by the Ford Foundation in 1956 to help research libraries take advantage of emerging technologies, the Council on Library Resources has shifted its purposes as well as its funding sources with each new president. It is only fitting, therefore, as the fifth president of the Council, for me to use this annual report to describe the directions for the future, even though such an exploration deviates from the norm of highlighting the past year's accomplishments.

One accomplishment is, however, important to cite here, because it has already led to significant changes in the inner workings of the Council. On March 1, 1995, the Council and the Commission on Preservation and Access formally affiliated, which means—in practical terms—sharing a president and reducing operating costs for both organizations. It is appropriate that these two organizations, both dedicated to assisting libraries and their users, have adopted the same cost-cutting techniques that have become a necessary commonplace among libraries today.

The Council, without an endowment as a safety net, has sought to cover a broad range of programs and projects in the past. Confronted by meager resources and the increasing reluctance of foundations to fund operating costs, the Council's Board of Directors in April adopted a plan to limit the program initiatives to three primary topics.

This decision, which was based on my own recommendations to the Board, will serve to set the direction of the Council for the next few years. Here is how I view that direction and the vital work that must be undertaken as the Council moves forward.

It is hard to know which is larger—the amount of “hype” swirling around the concept of the coming “Information Superhighway,” or the real potential that electronic access to information may have. Librarians are standing on the edge of developments that could magnify immeasurably the kinds and quantities of information that they can make accessible to their patrons. But they also are trying to find their way through a confusion of claims couched in technological jargon about what new technologies can and cannot do.

What Libraries Need

This much they do know: new expectations will be placed upon them. Already, the daily newspaper, the nightly newscast, and the professional journal all amplify the message that “obsolete” repositories of the past must give way to the “electronic library” of the future. Faculty members demand not only “CD-ROM” products for their teaching and research but also computer connections to electronic publications, various databases, and special networks for conversing with colleagues worldwide. Students anticipate that everything they need will be piped into their dorm-room computers, resembling the television sets with which they already are so familiar as sources of information and entertainment. Public and school libraries are no less under pressure to provide information in new as well as familiar forms, lest their patrons become “have-nots” in the highly competitive “information age.”

But how can librarians respond without training in the new technologies? Without money to install

electronic systems while maintaining print-based and other present collections? Without expertise in the economics of determining when and how and at what rate it makes financial sense to “digitize” a collection, buy into a “data service,” or create one for their own patrons? And without any clear and certain vision of what an “electronic library” is or eventually can be? Many libraries already have added electronic features to their services; but collectively they are far from ready to cope with a proliferation of information coming from an increasing number and variety of “publishers”—information that is likely to be unorganized, unstandardized, and out of bibliographic control.

The Council on Library Resources has a long and honorable career of helping libraries find their way past impediments on the road to better service. Overwhelming as present circumstances may seem, the Council can help again, particularly by renewing its leadership, but only if it focuses on the largest needs and searches for solutions of the highest quality.

In keeping with the Council’s traditions, I have proposed neither a program of indiscriminate spending nor an effort of the Council’s own to develop and decree solutions. Rather, the key concept is to help others solve problems, to promote successful project development in visible places, to foster models of high quality from which the library field can learn. Concentrating the Council’s resources on helping the most capable individuals and institutions build models of excellence in electronic librarianship is not elitism; it is a judicious use of severely limited resources to bring about achievements beneficial to libraries at large.

What I have recommended, and the Board has adopted, is a program focused on three activities that

seem best suited for the Council—areas in which we can work with real prospects for success. The three areas are: the development of leadership, the economics of information, and the transition to the electronic library.

New technologies have the power not only to transform information systems *within* such institutions as libraries; they have the power to transform those institutions from top to bottom, from inside and out. Libraries need leaders who can manage such transformations, who can recognize technological opportunities, make wise investment decisions, and control information technology for the benefit of library patrons. To develop such leaders means more than teaching them to use computer systems; it means equipping them with an understanding of how to work with users—scholars, teachers, students, public officials, community groups—to create, maintain, and manage electronic services through which those users can gain access to the particular kinds of information they need.

The Development of Leadership

The Council already is moving ahead in this area. The W. K. Kellogg Foundation has generously made available nearly \$1 million for work by the Council. We have formed an advisory committee to guide the Council in its use of these funds. The Council's grant is one of sixteen awarded by the Kellogg Foundation in a program for developing "Human Resources for Information Systems Management." The Foundation is enlisting the Council to help evaluate the results of the other grants and also to gather information in general on projects under development in public and school libraries—projects not just to purchase computers but to develop electronic information services with the specific needs of library patrons in mind. Kellogg funds also will enable the Council to provide small grants to aid in the development of some of the more promising projects, which could then serve as models for others.

More specifically, the Kellogg funds will enable the Council to support projects and exercise influence along the following lines:

*Transforming
Education*

- Evaluate current programs in schools of library and information science that electronically provide opportunities for “distance learning.” How do such programs function; how effective are they; how must they change to meet educational needs?
- Establish an institute, in collaboration with a university, to train mid- level librarians to manage in the electronic library environment.
- Gather information and produce case studies on curricular changes adopted by library schools in response to new information technologies—particularly changes in training professionals who will work in public and school libraries.
- Assess the potential of undergraduate programs of library and information studies.

Networking

- Identify programs now operational in public libraries that are extending or enhancing community-based information systems.
- Bring together from different parts of the country librarians who have successfully developed such programs in their communities.
- Work with public and school librarians to design programs through which other librarians can learn to provide community leadership on matters of information policy.

*Strengthening
Dialogue*

- Promote information sharing by convening, on a regular basis, the officers of foundations that are

interested in information policy, community advocacy, and public library programs designed to empower individuals and community groups.

- Commission a paper to describe the need for policies to enable community libraries to provide access to the kinds of information that people need in order to work and live productively; use the paper to stimulate wide-ranging discussions among librarians, community leaders, and citizens.

Most libraries have inadequate funds for the services they try to provide now, let alone for developing new ones by investing in electronic technologies. But the demand for such services, in today's atmosphere of budget cutting in public agencies at all levels, makes attention to the economics of librarianship unavoidable.

The Economics of Information

The issues are not just how to get the best bargains on hardware and software. The issues include how to test user interest in new services, how to estimate the costs of system creation and maintenance, what to expect in charges from data suppliers and copyright owners, what to budget for keeping data accessible (overcoming problems of hardware obsolescence and electronic-medium instability), and how to know when it is "cost effective" to scan material for electronic storage and access rather than continuing to retain it in a paper-based format. Attempts to reduce one kind of cost may simply increase another. Little research has been done on the economics of traditional libraries, let alone on electronic library systems and on costs of transition to them.

Added to the problem of inadequate resources is the lack of expertise of most librarians in cost accounting and economic modeling. Few libraries can adequately represent the actual costs of doing business. Librarians are not well prepared to compare the costs of delivering electronic information with more traditional

methods because they have not assembled economic data of current operations.

Accordingly, the Council already has assembled a distinguished group of economists who are willing to help us devise a program on the economics of information. These economists can assist the Council by identifying research needs and mapping out the dimensions of what librarians need to know—and how we can teach them—about the complex world of the costs of operations and the new emerging technologies that will assuredly transform those operations.

**The Transition to
the Electronic
Library**

Although the term is used frequently in the profession, agreement is rare on what an “electronic library” really is. Some speak of an electronic library as a collection of materials digitized or encoded for electronic transmission. Some speak of it as an institution that possesses, or an organization that controls, such materials. Some think of an electronic library as an agency that links existing institutions into a network for providing access to electronic information, establishing prices for it, providing finding aids to it, and protecting copyright restrictions on it. The term electronic library has been applied to consortia of collecting institutions, and even to research groups that have developed their own databases for use by networks of specialists in particular disciplines. As some see it, a library becomes electronic simply by adding CD-ROMs to its books and tape and video recordings, or by installing Internet-access computers next to its microform readers. To others, a library becomes electronic by scanning or keyboarding and encoding everything it has, so that it can make the entirety of its holdings electronically accessible anywhere.

However defined, the “electronic library” is appealing to librarians because it promises to help them do more of what they traditionally try to do—extend access to information. Yet for all the excitement, major obstacles remain in the way of electronic library development. New kinds of equipment are needed; new skills in its manage-

ment are required; new responsibilities arise for data protection; new methods are necessary to protect intellectual property rights; and agreement is needed on standards, on ways to prepare data for access by people who may be using different computers and different programs with different codes and different formats than those in which the available electronic files of data were generated.

There are five ways in which the Council could help. The first is to serve as a clearinghouse for information on developments. The second is to give special attention to the problems of "preserving" information in electronic forms. The third is to foster the creation of finding aids and other bibliographic controls to prevent users' being swamped by unorganized information. The fourth is to promote training for electronic library management. And the fifth is to undertake studies of the economics of electronic information.

In addition, however, the Council should also convene a special planning group, composed of people who are leaders in efforts to create *shared* electronic libraries; that is, systems to link electronically the information resources of multiple institutions. This group's purpose would be to identify the obstacles and determine what problems must be solved before such systems can be fully functional and widely available.

In the development of electronic capabilities, libraries must be able to look to models of achievement, models of excellence. What has worked for the pioneering institutions? What has not? What technologies are under development? What will be their effect? What can libraries do now, and expect to do in the future?

In the past, the Council has had interests that have sometimes ranged far beyond the borders I have set down. For example, the Council has long supported projects to assure control of bibliographic information and access to it. That concern, I believe, should be integrated

Some Other Possibilities

into the Council's concern with the emergence of the electronic library. Traditionally, the issue has been how to help people get information on the holdings of libraries other than their own. Now, it will be necessary to help users navigate the Internet to find what they want out of all the information being "dumped" into it. We can continue to give special attention to bibliographic control, within the agenda outlined above, so long as we succeed in finding the necessary funds to support it.

Intellectual property also has been a subject of special interest to the Council over the years. Copyright questions remain important and are subsumed within—not excluded from—the Council's three areas of focus. Furthermore, intellectual property issues are receiving some significant attention from the Commission on Preservation and Access, the Council's new affiliate. Together the Council and the Commission will be exploring the issue of intellectual property within the continuing debate over how the electronic library of the future will be defined.

Finally, the Council has previously made grants in support of "pure" research into library matters. Financial constraints are shaping a simple reality: there are fewer and fewer dollars at hand with which such research can be supported. Rather than treating research separately, the Council must now build provisions for research into all three of its primary areas of activity.

This activity—an agenda, really—grows out of and builds upon the Council's traditional strengths, interests, and concerns. It also recognizes that new technologies require new approaches. The Council's new course is designed to keep our work relevant to the problems that libraries must solve in this whirling age of technology and to provide models of excellence for the transitions that libraries must make into a future that has already arrived.

Deanna B. Marcum

Program Review

During this year of transition, the Council has concentrated most of its activity in program areas that have defined its primary concerns over the past three years: Human Resources, Economics, Infrastructure, and Access and Processing. Many of the major new activities took place in two areas—Human Resources (i.e., the program of leadership development supported by the W. K. Kellogg Foundation) and Infrastructure (i.e., the National Engineering Information Initiative). Nevertheless, several previously supported projects in the areas of Economics and Access and Processing reached their end and reported on their research results.

New technology not only has the power to transform information systems within institutions; it has the power to transform the institutions themselves. Libraries, like other institutions, need leaders who can manage these dramatic transformations, recognize technological opportunities, make wise investment decisions, and control information technology for the benefit of library patrons. In the new technological era, libraries must depend on leaders who understand how to work with users, community groups, public officials, teachers, students, and scholars. Library patrons may come looking for books, even in this age of computer networking; but they also come looking for much, much more. Leadership in the library world means knowing how to create, maintain, and manage services by keeping the needs of users in mind. The job of providing information is not, in that sense, very different than it has been in any other era. Now, however, the challenge is to master the growing technology in such a way as to meet—and even go beyond—the expectations of users, whether they are thumbing through an old card catalog or exploring the growing electronic web of information.

Human Resources

Relying on support from the W. K. Kellogg Foundation, the Council on Library Resources is working to develop the kind of library leadership that will be prepared to confront the new era. Toward that end, the Council has received one of sixteen grants from the Kellogg Foundation in a program called "Human Resources for Information Systems Management." CLR will assist Kellogg in its overall program by fostering discussions about new technologies and the transformation of information systems, gathering information on projects under development in libraries that are providing innovative services, bringing groups together that otherwise might not interact, and helping assess the results of the other grants in Kellogg's emerging program.

*Information Services
Leadership Program*

The Council gave its support to several projects aimed at encouraging and strengthening dialogue among library and community leaders.

- The St. Paul Public Library completed a comprehensive long-range planning process that involved public participation in focus groups, steering committee deliberations, and a Mayor's Forum.
- On April 8-9 1995, the Urban Libraries Council (ULC) sponsored a conference for ULC library directors and trustees to address leadership development in a political environment.
- A Montana State University librarian and an assistant professor in the Department of Political Science conducted workshops on assessing electronic library services for local government officials.
- The Montgomery County (Maryland) Department of Public Libraries, with the assistance of the Montgomery County Public Schools Division of Media and Educational Technology, held a meeting of practitioners and administrators to address the issues of public school and public library cooperation on December 9, 1994.

- Drawing on the experience of librarians from many different groups, the Library and Information Technology Association has begun to build a network of librarians who can serve as a major resource for dealing with library issues in the evolution of the National Information Infrastructure (NII).

Studies supported by the Council resulted in a number of reports (for full bibliographical citations, see Publications and Reports Resulting from CLR Programs, page 32). Dr. Larry Hardesty, the coordinator of the College Library Director Mentor Program (sponsored by the ACRL College Library Section Leadership Committee), reported that in the program's third year it paired fifteen new directors with experienced directors who served as mentors. Dr. Hardesty also is investigating the recent interest among college administrators to combine libraries and computing centers under a single supervisor. W. Michael Havener and Wilbur A. Stolt, reporting on the results of their 1991 study, published an article based on a cooperative research project to investigate the role that institutional support plays in the professional development of academic libraries. In two articles based on her dissertation, Tina Maragou Hovekamp assessed the effects of organized labor on the organizational commitment and job satisfaction of professional librarians.

Research and Reports

The Council, continuing its long-standing interest in economic issues, stimulated research in the costs and benefits of library operations by supporting several projects. At a time when new information technologies are rapidly becoming available, library managers are forced to make difficult choices between old and new information systems. While new systems are increasingly available, new sources of funding are not. Library managers need to know the real costs of services if they are to make credible, supportable decisions. The Council is committed to providing useful assessment tools to help librarians and information managers reach a better understanding of the economic issues that are shaping their realities.

Economics

*Development of
New Techniques*

Technology has generated a range of opportunities—and some very specific needs—for developing new approaches in the cost management of library and information services. The Council provided support to several projects that sought to improve the efficiencies of information delivery.

- Building on quality improvement modules borrowed from the Intel Corporation, the University of Arizona libraries have pinpointed library processes in which to identify, train, and implement teams in “process improvement” techniques.
- Investigators from the School of Information and Library Studies and the University Libraries, University at Buffalo, SUNY, were granted funds to introduce Statistical Quality Control (SQC) and Statistical Process Control (SPC) techniques—developed from the total quality management philosophy—into an interlibrary loan operation.
- Using the contract services of the Association of Research Libraries (Office of Management Services), the Council tested the applicability of benchmarking techniques in academic research libraries by studying three interlibrary loan processes (borrowing, lending, and delivery) in three different academic institutions.

*Identifying Costs and
Benefits*

Questions of costs are at the heart of the new electronic technology, and the Council has put its efforts into discerning, with as much accuracy as possible, the costs of library and information services in the present and in the future. The Council has also supported project that analyze the transition from print to electronic delivery of information.

- With the Council’s support, the Coalition for Networked Information has prepared a white paper

that addresses the question of how cost structures will change as the world of print is transformed into an electronic network.

- The final technical report of a fifteen-month project to evaluate the costs and value of library functions at five major research libraries was completed by Paul Kantor, Joanna D'Esposito-Wachtmann, and Tefko Saracevic of the Alexandria Project Laboratory, School of Communication Information and Library Studies, Rutgers, the State University of New Jersey.
- At the State University of New York at Albany, Binghamton, Buffalo, and Stony Brook, the costs and benefits of access to scholarly articles are being investigated by the university libraries.
- This year, the North American Interlibrary Loan and Document (NAILDD) Project, which was developed by the Association of Research Libraries (with support from the Council), continued its work identifying technological improvements that can be made in interlibrary loan operations.

Research on economic issues produced some important publications and reports (for full bibliographical citations, see Publications and Reports Resulting from CLR Programs, page 32). In a recent book, Joseph A. McDonald and Lynda Basney Micikas considered the effectiveness of small academic libraries from the perspective of the library's relationship to its parent organization. Comparing two current periodical use studies that employed different methodologies and were conducted four years apart in the Science and Engineering Library at the University at Buffalo, Maiken Naylor revealed how such studies must be carefully handled in light of under-reporting by indifferent users and over-reporting of favorite titles by enthusiastic users. Eleanor Gossen and Suzanne Irving

*Research and
Reports*

analyzed low-use periodicals and determined that it was cost-effective to rely on interlibrary loan or commercial document delivery for article access, even when subscription prices for the titles were modest. In an important article, George A. Chressanthis and June D. Chressanthis analyzed the components of library subscription prices among the top-ranked economics journals.

Infrastructure

The Council's infrastructure program focuses on the systems, services, and facilities that exist outside libraries and that help them operate more effectively. Under this definition, infrastructure includes parent organizations, communication networks, utilities, vendors, and the publishing industry. Through this program, the Council tries to facilitate communication to make sure the sweeping forces of change—including economic, sociopolitical, technical and legal alterations—do not inhibit access to information by individuals and groups.

National Engineering Information Initiative

In December 1994, the Council announced the transfer of all activities to develop the National Engineering Information Initiative (NEII) to the American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE), a nonprofit association of individuals and organizations founded in 1893 and dedicated to promoting excellence in engineering and engineering technology education. Over the past year, the Council has supported various projects designed to enhance communications among engineers.

- The Engineering Library at Cornell University, with the Council's support, developed Internet Connections for Engineering (ICE) and provided electronic resources available from a variety of sources.
- *Communication by Engineers: A Literature Review of Engineers' Information Needs, Seeking Processes, and Use*, an annotated bibliography, was

prepared by Donald W. King, with the assistance of Jane Castro and Heather Jones, for the Council on Library Resources under a contract with the University of Tennessee, Center for Information Studies, Graduate School of Library and Information Science.

The Council has worked to encourage communications between—and among—the various constituencies that comprise the library and information infrastructure.

*Scholarly
Communications*

- The Joint Working Group on Professional and Scholarly Information in the Electronic Age, established under the sponsorship of the Council on Library Resources and the Professional/Scholarly Publishing Division of the Association of American Publishers, Inc., issued a report on the role of librarians and publishers in the scholarly information process.

- An article by Henry W. Riecken, published in 1994, was originally prepared as a background paper for the Council's Research Library Committee to provide a context for their discussions about the future of the academic research library.

With a strong belief in the value of teamwork and information sharing, the Council has supported a number of projects intended to forge institutional cooperation as a key element in the infrastructure of information.

*Institutional
Cooperation*

- The New York State Library and the New York State Archives and Records Administration have developed a prototype state government information locator system that will provide common access regardless of format or location.

- At Rice University, several members of the academic community there—including a librarian, a

senior faculty member in the history department, some computing professionals, and a team of student programmers—designed and developed a hypertextual, multimedia educational resource to be used in a course on the history of science.

- With the Council's support, Towson State University in Maryland is involved in a strategic planning process to integrate information resources within the campus planning context.

- Making the transition to the National Information Infrastructure was the theme of the Library of Congress Network Advisory Committee's December 1994 meeting, which featured industry representatives who discussed how their roles will change as networking expands from the academic to the commercial markets.

- The Library Research Center of the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign is administering a national survey of public libraries and local governments to study the attitudes of municipal and county officials toward public libraries.

Research and Reports

In an article published in 1995, Judith Adams and Sharon C. Bonk investigated the use of electronic information technologies by university faculty on four campuses and found a lack of equality in access to technologies among the academic disciplines (for full bibliographic citations see *Publications and Reports Resulting from CLR Programs*, p. 32). Testing the validity of studies previously conducted by Robert F. Munn in the late 1960s and William Moffett in the early 1980s, Lloyd W. Chapin and Larry Hardesty—in a re-publication of their research—summarized their examination of how academic administrators view college libraries and concluded that apparent satisfaction among administrators today masks what otherwise might be called benign neglect.

**Access and
Processing**

The Council has initiated important projects that have evaluated the means by which libraries acquire, organize, store, retrieve, reproduce, and make available information. In its Access and Processing programs, the Council supports innovative methods that enhance access to information and improve the internal processes of libraries and other information delivery systems.

Access Tools

New or enhanced tools can often help libraries refine their operations or expand into different areas of service. These tools, like those of any machinist, enable libraries to build better and more efficient mechanisms.

- The Council is supporting preparation of a third edition of *Library of Congress Subject Headings: Principles and Application*, a primary tool for bibliographic access. Lois Mai Chan of the School of Library and Information Science at the University of Kentucky is updating her popular and useful work.
- Marcia J. Bates, University of California at Los Angeles, completed her analysis of how additional vocabulary could be added to the machine-readable database of the Library of Congress Subject Headings and recommended a cluster method.
- In a meeting organized by Laura Stalker of the Huntington Library, the Working Group on Form and Genre Vocabularies convened its annual conference to reconcile another set of form and genre terminologies in major published thesauri.
- Project investigators at Cornell University are developing a multimedia collection access tool to support the design and development of remote access to images that can be used in the research and teaching process.

- Thomas Hickerson, Carl A. Kroch Library, and Geri Day, Department of Communication, Cornell University, are investigating how users from a variety of disciplines—as well as levels of education and expertise—take advantage of new technologies for educational experiences.
- Charles Hildreth is examining the current state of the most common access tool, the online catalog, with a view toward assisting information system designers and librarians plan for the catalog of the future.

*Information
Seeking*

The ways in which users seek information are vitally important to librarians, particularly in this era of rapid communication of information and new information media. The Council has supported several studies that explore how users acquire information.

- At Grinnell College, Gail Bonath, a librarian, and Janet Gibson, a cognitive psychologist, are identifying expert (i.e., librarian) and novice (i. e., liberal arts college undergraduate) concepts that influence research steps in the use of online catalogs.
- Another cooperative research project at Dickinson College, under the direction of Kristin Senecal from the library and Michael Holden from the chemistry department, is helping undergraduate students understand the nature of scientific communication by monitoring the way they follow the trail of references about chemical reactions back to seminal articles.
- Peling Wang and Marilyn White of the University of Maryland at College Park, are tracking the utility of documents requested and used by researchers at

different stages of their research projects to learn how their assessments of document relevance change over time.

The Council has been a long-time supporter of national and international programs for shared cataloging. The current Program for Cooperative Cataloging (PCC) evolved from the work of the Cooperative Cataloging Council (CCC), which was established in 1993 with partial support from CLR to develop a useful strategic plan for increasing the effectiveness of cooperative cataloging among the nation's libraries. The CCC created a set of task forces to focus on specific goals and objectives, and results of the task force investigations and acceptance of their recommendations led to the establishment of the PCC. The Council on Library Resources has continued its support for specific task force investigations. The details of the development of the PCC are available in a new publication about the history of the CCC, *Towards a New Beginning in Cooperative Cataloging: The History, Progress, and Future of the Cooperative Cataloging Council*, prepared by staff at the Library of Congress.

Improved Processing

- Susan A. Massey and S. Michael Malinconico of the University of Alabama are undertaking a cooperative research project to measure the accuracy rates of samples of incoming cataloging copy and determine whether a policy of accepting that cataloging copy without shelving will create significant disarrangement of a local online shelflist.

A substantial amount of publications and reports were issued as a result of the Council's support of various research projects (for full bibliographical citations, see Publications and Reports Resulting from CLR Programs, page 32). With the support of a 1983 planning grant from the Council, the American Historical Association has pub-

Research and Reports

lished the third edition of its guide to historical literature. A monograph on legal research (including a final chapter on the influence of electronic technology) by George S. Grossman was an outgrowth of his CLR Fellowship. John Richardson's CLR-supported research to identify the rules at work in a general reference dialogue was incorporated into a monograph on knowledge-based systems for general reference work.

Martha Andrews of the Institute of Arctic and Alpine Research, University of Colorado, reported on the distribution of responsibilities of accessioning and indexing arctic regions information outlined in the plan she developed with CLR support to the Polar Libraries Colloquy. Titia van der Werf-Davelaar, a 1991 Robert Vosper IFLA Fellow, described her investigation of an end-user technology called PIT (Personal Information Technology) and revealed that libraries generally still consider end-user systems to be those that deliver information through library systems.

Reporting on their study of the effects of computer tutorials on student searches for information, Joan M. Cherry, Weijing Yuian, and Marshall Clinton of the University of Toronto found that search performance was not necessarily enhanced by the use of a tutorial. Users are persistent when it comes to finding the information they need, but Stephen E. Wiberley, Jr., Robert Allen Daugherty, and James A. Danowski at the University of Illinois at Chicago, in an article published in 1995, found that users generally display 30-35 postings (although the most persistent will look up as many as 200 postings) and will abandon online catalog searches if they are overloaded with too much information. Willy Cromwell of Stanford University (and chair of one of the task forces for the Cooperative Cataloging Council) described the development of the "core" bibliographic record concept in an article published in October 1994. In an article published in 1994 in *IFLA Journal*, Georgeta Clinca, an IFLA Robert Vosper Fellow,

discussed how cataloging-in-publication (CIP) operations provide rapid and improved access to standardized bibliographic information for many nations. Another IFLA Fellow, Craig R. Fairley, reported on the progress of implementation of electronic data interchange on library operations.

Committees

Marilyn Gell Mason (Chair), Cleveland Public Library
Robert B. Croneberger, Carnegie Library of Pittsburgh
Martin Gomez, Oakland Public Library
Joey Rodger, Urban Libraries Council
Elizabeth Stroup, Seattle Public Library
John Tyson, University of Tennessee at Knoxville

*Kellogg Project
Advisory Committee*

Meredith Butler, University at Albany, SUNY
Jerry Campbell, Duke University
George Chressanthis, Mississippi State University
Colin Day, University of Michigan Press
Michael McPherson (Chair), Williams College

*Committee on
Economics*

David F. Bishop, Northwestern University
Anita Branin, University of Minnesota
Martin M. Cummings (Chair), Director Emeritus, National Library of Medicine
Ronald L. Larsen, University of Maryland
Carol A. Mandel, Columbia University
Margaret A. Otto, Dartmouth College
Shelley Phipps, University of Arizona
Henry W. Riecken, Kezar Associates, Washington, D.C.

Review Committee

**Publications and
Reports Resulting
from CLR Pro-
grams, 1994/1995**

*Part I. Publications of
the Council and CRL
Staff*

CLR Reports (newsletter, irregularly published).

King, Donald W. *Communication by Engineers: A Literature Review of Engineers' Information Needs, Seeking Processes, and Use*. Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, 1994.

Librarians and Publishers in the Scholarly Information Process: Transition in the Electronic Age; a report from the Joint Working Group on Professional and Scholarly Information in the Electronic Age under the sponsorship of the Council on Library Resources and the Professional/Scholarly Publishing Division, Association of American Publishers, Inc. Report prepared by Linda Scovill. Washington, D.C. : Council on Library Resources; New York, N.Y.: Association of American Publishers, Inc., 1995.

Penniman, W. David. "Libraries: Overview." In *Encyclopedia of the Future*. New York, N.Y.: Macmillan Reference [in press].

Timmer, Ellen B. "Council on Library Resources, 1994." In *The Bowker Annual Library and Book Trade Almanac, 40th ed.*, 282-291. New Providence, N.J.: Bowker, 1995.

*Part II. Publications
by Grant Recipients
and Contractors*

Adams, Judith A. and Sharon C. Bonk. "Electronic Information Technologies and Resources: Use by University Faculty and Faculty Preferences for Related Library Services." *College & Research Libraries* 56, no. 2 (March 1995): 119-131.

The American Historical Association's Guide to Historical Literature. 3rd ed. New York, N.Y.: Oxford University Press, 1995. ISBN 0-19-505727-9

Andrews, Martha. "Are We Information Poor? Limitations to Accessing Polar Literature." In *Proceedings of the 5th Polar Libraries Colloquy, July 3-8, 1994*, 5-7. Cambridge, U.K.: Published for Polar Libraries Colloquy Steering Committee by Luntisham Books, 1995.

Chapin, Lloyd W. and Larry Hardesty. "Benign Neglect of the 'Heart of the College': Liberal Arts College Deans Look at the Library." In *Academic Libraries: Their Rationale and Role in American Higher Education*, 29-41. Westport, Conn.: Greenwood Press, 1995.

Cherry, Joan M., Weijing Yuan, and Marshall Clinton. "Evaluating the Effectiveness of a Concept-based Computer Tutorial for OPAC Users." *College & Research Libraries* 55, no. 4 (July 1994): 355-364.

Chressanthis, George A. and June D. Chressanthis. "The Determinants of Library Subscription Prices of the Top-Ranked Economics Journals: An Econometric Analysis." *The Journal of Economic Education* 25, no. 4 (Fall 1994): 367-82.

Clinca, Georgeta. "The Functioning of CIP." *IFLA Journal* 20, no. 4 (1994): 478-487.

Cromwell, Willy. "The Core Record: A New Bibliographic Standard." *Library Resources & Technical Services* 38, no. 4 (October 1994): 415-430.

Fairley, Craig R. *The Impact of Electronic Data Interchange on Library Operations: Implementation Issues*. The Hague, Netherlands: IFLA, 1995. ISBN 90-70916-52-5

Gossen, Eleanor A. and Suzanne Irving. "Ownership versus Access and Low-Use Periodical Titles." *Library Resources & Technical Services* 39, no. 1 (January 1995): 43-52.

Grossman, George S. *Legal Research: Historical Foundations of the Electronic Age*. New York, N.Y.: Oxford University Press, 1994. ISBN 0-19-508637-6

Havener, W. Michael and Wilbur A. Stolt. "The Professional Development Activities of Academic Librarians; Does Institutional Support Make a Difference?" *College & Research Libraries* 55, no. 1 (January 1994): 25-36.

Hovekamp, Tina Maragou. "Organizational Commitment of Professional Employees in Union and Nonunion Research Libraries." *College & Research Libraries* 55, no. 4 (July 1994): 297-307.

_____. "Unionization and Job Satisfaction among Professional Library Employees in Academic Research Institutions." *College & Research Libraries* 56, no. 4 (July 1995): 341-350.

Kingma, Bruce. "Access to Journal Articles: A Model of the Cost Efficiency of Document Delivery and Library Consortia." In *Proceedings of the 57th ASIS Annual Meeting*, 8-16. Medford, N.J.: Published for the American Society for Information Science by Learned Information, 1994.

McDonald, Joseph A. and Lynda Basney Micikas. *Academic Libraries: The Dimensions of Their Effectiveness*. Westport, Conn.: Greenwood, 1994. ISBN 0-313-27269-7

Naylor, Maiken. "Comparative Results of Two Current Periodical Use Studies." *Library Resources & Technical Services* 38, no. 4 (October 1994): 373-388.

Network Content—A Dialogue with Publishers: Proceedings of the Library of Congress Network Advisory Committee Meeting, December 12-14, 1993. Network Planning Paper 26. Washington, D.C.: Library of Congress, 1994.

Richardson, John V. *Knowledge-Based Systems for General Reference Work: Applications, Problems, and Progress*. San Diego, Calif.: Academic Press, 1995. ISBN 0-12-588460-5

Riecken, Henry W. "Scholarly Publication: Are There Viable

Options?" *Centennial Review* 38, no. 3 (Fall 1994): 447-477.

Towards a New Beginning in Cooperative Cataloging: The History, Progress, and Future of the Cooperative Cataloging Council. Washington, D.C.: Library of Congress Cataloging Distribution Service for the Regional & Cooperative Cataloging Division, 1994.

van der Werf-Davelaar, Titia. "Access to Library Services by Means of End-User Technology." *IFLA Journal* 20, no. 4 (1994): 462-477.

Wiberley, Stephen E., Jr., Robert Allen Daugherty, and James A. Danowski. "User Persistence in Displaying Online Catalog Postings: LUIS." *Library Resources & Technical Services* 39, no. 3 (July 1995): 247-264.

Many project reports are published in the professional literature. Authors retain ownership of the reports and are asked to submit copies to the ERIC database. ERIC document numbers that have been reported to CLR are listed at the end of the citation. Inquiries about reports without an ERIC numbers should be addressed to the primary author or contact person.

*Part III. Project
Reports Received*

Association of Research Libraries. Office of Management Services. "The CLR Pilot Benchmarking Project: Interlibrary Loan Pilot Benchmark Study." Part I. By International Systems Services Corporation, July 6, 1994. Part II: Analysis of ILL Operations in Academic Libraries Arising from the Study. By Jack A. Siggins. September 15, 1994.

Bates, Marcia J. "Expanded Entry Vocabulary for the Library of Congress Subject Headings; Final Report." Los Angeles, Calif. July 1994.

"Beyond the Internet: The Transition to the National Information Infrastructure." Papers from the Library of Congress Network Advisory Committee, December 4-5, 1994. Network

Planning Papers 28. Available from LC MARVEL: Libraries and Publishers (Technical Services)/ Library & Information Technology Organizations/ Network Advisory Committee.

Burr, Elizabeth S. "The Role of Librarians in the Creation of Online Curricula Resources." Final Report on the Galileo Project. Houston, Tex. Rice University. December 15, 1994. <http://is.rice.edu/~esb/clr.html> or <http://is.rice.edu/~esb/galileo.html>

"Community Connections: The National Infrastructure and Civic Networks." Papers from the Library of Congress Network Advisory Committee, June 12-14, 1994. Network Planning Papers 27. Available from LC MARVEL: Libraries and Publishers (Technical Services)/ Library & Information Technology Organizations/ Network Advisory Committee.

Hardesty, Larry. "The College Library Director Mentor Program." [Second Year Report]. Eckerd College. September 1994.

Kantor, Paul, Joanna D'Esposito-Wachtmann, and Tefko Saracevic. "Cost and Beneficial Impacts of Library Services: Final Report." [New Brunswick, N.J.]: Alexandria Project Laboratory, School of Communication Information and Library Studies, Rutgers, the State University of New Jersey. 1994. Technical Report APLAB/94-3
<ftp://scils.rutgers.edu/pub/APLab/Cost.Value.Study>

Powell, Jill, Bill Jenkins, and John Saylor. "ICE (Internet Connections for Engineering) Final Report." Ithaca, N.Y., Engineering Library. Cornell University. June 1995.

**Program Guidelines
and Grant Application
Procedures**

The Council on Library Resources supports work by individuals and organizations on matters pertinent to libraries and information services, with a primary objective of improving their quality and performance. Individuals with specific interests and expertise are encouraged to take the initiative and propose for consideration projects within the Council's program areas. In addition to the General Program grants, the Council sponsors a Cooperative Research Program, which supports projects proposed jointly by librarians and members of faculties in library or information sciences or, when appropriate, other pertinent scholarly disciplines. The Council's program areas are:

- *Leadership Development.* To encourage innovative ideas for preparing future leaders who will manage new information technologies and systems. Proposals for public library leadership development are especially encouraged.
- *Economics of Information Services.* To promote research that analyzes the costs and benefits of traditional and evolving library services and investigate the economic issues of the transition to electronic library systems.
- *Transition from the Traditional to the Electronic Library.* To bring attention to the specific issues faced by libraries generally as they develop electronic services appropriate for their communities and to promote models of excellence in the transition to the electronic library.

Initial inquiries should state the purpose of the proposed work, indicate methodology, establish the credentials of the responsible individuals, and provide an estimate of the total costs and funding requirements. The Council will respond promptly with an indication of interest. If subsequent exploration seems justified, preparation of a complete proposal will be suggested.

*Application
Procedures*

Full documentation should include:

1. A concise description of the proposed project.
2. A thorough explanation of the work to be done, including project objectives and method to be employed. A timetable, pertinent background information, and plans for evaluation of results should also be provided.
3. A detailed budget linking costs to project components.
4. Concise and pertinent curricula vitae of the principal investigators.

Proposals are carefully reviewed by the Council staff and, when necessary, external advisers, who consider such matters as relevance to current Council interests and activities; relationship to other, similar work; projected costs in the context of the work described; and the importance of anticipated results. The Council also looks for evidence of institutional support, including cost sharing. With the exception of a few cyclical programs, there are no submission deadlines. In many cases, grant applications are also reviewed by an external proposal review committee, and proposals over \$25,000 require approval from the Council Board, which meets twice a year (usually in May and November). Proposals that are to be recommended for Board approval cannot always be reviewed in time to be presented at the first meeting following their receipt. All inquiries and proposals are reported to the Board, including those declined at the staff and review committee level.

Exclusions

Support is not provided for construction, renovation, or other capital improvements; collection acquisitions; routine operating costs; data conversion; activities judged to be of limited influence; or work that essentially repeats previous research. The Council does not

fund indirect costs. Equipment purchases are also generally not supported, unless integral to a research project. While the Council, in consultation with its advisers, often initiates and promotes work in program areas, exploratory correspondence and conversation are always welcome, and all proposals receive careful consideration.

Inquiries should be addressed to Program Officer, Council on Library Resources, 1400 16th St., N.W., Suite 715, Washington, DC 20036-2217 (202-939-3370 voice, 202-939-3499 fax, gwlafant@cpa.org Internet).

Contact

**Grants and Contracts Active
in Fiscal 1995**

(unaudited)

	Unpaid (6/30/94)	Grants & Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid (6/30/95)
Association of Research Libraries Washington, DC				
ARL visiting program officer	700	0	0	700
Benchmarking pilot project	5,040	0	5,040	0
International conference on total quality management and academic libraries	250	0	0	250
Bates, Marcia Van Nuys, CA				
Examine the possibility of expanded entry vocabulary for Library of Congress subject headings	6,000	0	6,000	0
California State University Chico, CA				
Packet radio Internet extension	1,048	0	0	1,048
Coalition for Networked Information Washington, DC				
To establish an analytical framework and baseline for networked information resources and services	25,000	0	12,000	13,000
Cornell University Engineering Library Ithaca, NY				
Managing engineering information resources on the Internet	1,000	0	0	1,000

	Unpaid (6/30/94)	Grants & Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid (6/30/95)
Cornell University Library Ithaca, NY				
Development of a multimedia collection access tool	24,677	0	12,000	12,677
Dickinson College Carlisle, PA				
Bibliographic instruction in the field of chemistry	1,900	0	1,900	0
Eckerd College St. Petersburg, FL				
College library director mentor program (1992-1994)	4,000	0 (6,198)	0 (2,198)	0
College library director mentor program (1994-1996)	22,600	0 (18,042)	11,000 (6,442)	0
Grinnell College Grinnell, IA				
Expertise and subjects' mental models of online catalogs	0	1,820	1,700	120
Hildreth Charles R. Norman, OK				
Study of functionality of online catalogs	9,000	0	0	9,000
Indiana University Bloomington, IN				
NASA knowledge diffusion research project	568	0	0	568

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	Unpaid (6/30/94)	Grants & Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid (6/30/95)
Japan Information Access Project Washington, DC				
Symposium on access use and demand for Japanese information	500	0	500	0
Johns Hopkins University Baltimore, MD				
Information-seeking process among population studies researchers	500	0	0	500
Library and Information Technology Association Chicago, IL				
Forum in telecommunications and information infrastructure policy issues	5,000	0	5,000	0
National Information Standards Organization Bethesda, MD				
Development of technical standards for the <i>preservation of library materials</i>	10,000	0 (4,977)	1,523	3,500
New York State Library Albany, NY				
New York State information locator system prototype	0	24,880	22,000	2,880
Queens College Flushing, NY				
Seminar series on mapping curricular <i>revision</i>	3,100	0 (107)	2,993	0

	Unpaid (6/30/94)	Grants & Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid
Rice University				
Houston, TX				
The Rice humanities electronic studio	5,000	0	5,000	0
Rutgers University				
New Brunswick, NJ				
Study of the costs and beneficial impacts of library functions	12,612	0	0	12,612
Special Libraries Association				
Washington, DC				
Development of continuing education course on total quality management	5,548	0 (5,548)	0	0
Towson State University				
Towson, MD				
Strategic planning for information resources	1,000	0	0	1,000
University at Albany Foundation				
Albany, NY				
Study of cost-benefits of access compared to ownership costs for high-cost research journals	39,012	0	20,000	19,012
University at Buffalo, State University of New York				
Buffalo, NY				
Statistical process control of interlibrary loan for continuous quality improvement	0	28,090	13,500	14,590

	Unpaid (6/30/94)	Grants & Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid
University of Alabama Tuscaloosa, AL				
Local shelflisting of LC classification call numbers from OCLC cataloging copy	0	2,953	2,700	253
University of Arizona Tuscon, AZ				
Databased process improvement in a team-based learning organization	0	24,000	22,000	2,000
University of California Santa Cruz, CA				
Study of search patterns of in-library online catalog users	283	0	0	283
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign Champaign, IL				
Study of attitudes of municipal and county officials toward public libraries	1,000	0	0	1,000
University of Kentucky Lexington, KY				
Preparation of the third edition of Library of Congress Subject Headings: Principles and Application	0	2,450	2,200	250
University of Maryland at College Park College Park, MD				
Document selection and relevance assessments during a research project	0	2,616	2,500	116

	Unpaid (6/30/94)	Grants & Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid
University of Tennessee Knoxville, TN				
An annotated bibliography of the information needs and information-seeking habits of scientists and engineers	800	0 (800)	0	0
University of Texas Austin, TX				
Seminar on academic library assessment factors	1,700	0 (218)	1,700 (218)	0
Current year adjustments; other refunds and adjustments from prior years' grants and contracts	0	(39)	(39)	0
Totals	\$ 187,838	\$ 86,809 \$ (35,929)	\$ 151,256 \$ (8,897)	\$ 96,359

Independent Auditors' Report

To the Board of Directors

Council on Library Resources, Inc.
Washington, D.C.

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC. (the "Council") as of June 30, 1995, and the related statements of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the years then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit. We have previously audited and reported on the financial statements presented for the preceding year. Information for the year ended June 30, 1994 is presented for comparative purposes only and was extracted from the financial statements for that year, on which an unqualified opinion dated August 30, 1994 was presented.

We conducted our audit in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC. as of June 30, 1995, and the results of its operations and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The accompanying supplementary information is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and, in our opinion, is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Hoffman Dykes & Fitzgerald, P.C.

Vienna, Virginia
September 7, 1995

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Financial Position

June 30, 1995

(with Comparative Totals for June 30, 1994)

	<u>1995</u>	<u>1994</u>
Assets		
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 186,646	\$ 323,800
Investments	1,275,961	1,567,475
Grant receivable - temporarily restricted	520,000	520,000
Other assets	<u>29,091</u>	<u>30,336</u>
Total assets	<u>\$2,011,698</u>	<u>\$2,441,611</u>
 Liabilities and Net Assets		
Accounts payable and accrued expenses	\$ 28,484	\$ 22,784
Grants payable:		
Unrestricted	40,737	87,928
Restricted	<u>55,622</u>	<u>99,910</u>
	<u>96,359</u>	<u>187,838</u>
Total liabilities	124,843	210,622
Commitments	-	-
 Net Assets:		
Unrestricted	807,966	939,476
Temporarily restricted	<u>1,078,889</u>	<u>1,291,513</u>
Total net assets	<u>1,886,855</u>	<u>2,230,989</u>
Total liabilities and net assets	<u>\$2,011,698</u>	<u>\$2,441,611</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

**Statement of Activities and Changes in Net Assets
for the Year Ended June 30, 1995**

(with Comparative Totals for the Year Ended June 30, 1994)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 1995</u>	<u>Total 1994</u>
Revenue:				
Grants	\$ -	\$ 350,000	\$ 350,000	\$ 991,798
Interest income	88,314	-	88,314	60,656
Other income, principally publication sales	13,269	-	13,269	-
Net Assets Released from Restrictions:				
Satisfaction of program restrictions	145,957	(145,957)	-	-
Expiration of time restrictions	<u>416,667</u>	<u>(416,667)</u>	-	-
Total net assets released from restrictions	<u>562,624</u>	<u>(562,624)</u>	-	-
Total revenue	664,207	(212,624)	451,583	1,052,454
Expenses:				
Program services:				
Human resources	172,319	-	172,319	100,891
Access and processing	67,095	-	67,095	97,881
Economics	119,403	-	119,403	175,136
Infrastructure	<u>162,898</u>	-	<u>162,898</u>	<u>274,792</u>
Total program services expenses	521,715	-	521,715	648,700
Development	29,234	-	29,234	113,659
Administration	<u>244,768</u>	-	<u>244,768</u>	<u>251,634</u>
Total expenses	<u>795,717</u>	-	<u>795,717</u>	<u>1,013,993</u>
Cumulative effect on prior year of a change in method of accounting for grants and contracts	-	-	-	<u>742,131</u>
Change in Net Assets	(131,510)	(212,624)	(344,134)	780,592
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>939,476</u>	<u>1,291,513</u>	<u>2,230,989</u>	<u>1,450,397</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$807,966</u>	<u>\$1,078,889</u>	<u>\$1,886,855</u>	<u>\$2,230,989</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Cash Flows
For the Year Ended June 30, 1995

(with Comparative Totals for the Year Ended June 30, 1994)

	1995	1994
Cash Flows from Operating Activities:		
Change in net assets	\$ (344,134)	\$ 780,592
Cumulative effect on prior year of a change in method of accounting for grants and contracts:		
Temporarily restricted net assets	-	(742,131)
(Increase) decrease in:		
Grant receivable	-	(7,000)
Other assets	1,245	8,867
Increase (decrease) in:		
Accounts payable and accrued expense	5,700	5,217
Grants payable	<u>(91,479)</u>	<u>(122,493)</u>
Net cash used in operating activities	<u>(428,668)</u>	<u>(76,948)</u>
Cash Flows from Investing Activities:		
Sale of investments	2,832,419	2,542,367
Purchase of investments	<u>(2,540,905)</u>	<u>(2,349,675)</u>
Net cash provided by investing activities	<u>291,514</u>	<u>192,692</u>
Net (Decrease) Increase in Cash and Cash Equivalents	(137,154)	115,744
Cash and Cash Equivalents, Beginning of Year	<u>323,800</u>	<u>208,056</u>
Cash and Cash Equivalents, End of Year	<u>\$ 186,646</u>	<u>\$ 323,800</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements

Notes to Financial Statements

June 30, 1995

A Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research.

The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work directly through administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

B Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting

The accompanying financial statements of the Council have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions

The Council reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When a grantor time restriction expires or expenditures are made that satisfy the restricted purpose of those grants, the purpose of the restriction is accomplished and temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the Statement of Activities as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Grants and contracts payable

Grants and contracts made by the Council are recorded as grants and contracts payable and as an expense at the time recipients are awarded the grants or contracts. Current period expenses are reduced for grant or contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets

The Board of Directors has designated a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects. Also, \$300,000 was designated as an administrative reserve to cover future operating needs of the Council.

Cash and cash equivalents

For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market mutual fund and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Investments

Investments which consist of treasury bills, of which approximately \$322,000 is temporarily restricted, are recorded at cost which approximates market. Interest which is not restricted by the related grants is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs which include rent and other expenses are identified as support services costs and have been allocated directly to programs, development and administration on a systematic basis. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs, development and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Contributions

The Council records grants and contracts received as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending on the existence and/or nature of any grantor restrictions. Time-restricted grants and contracts are reported as temporarily restricted support and are reclassified to unrestricted net assets upon expiration of the restriction.

Financial statement presentation

In 1994, the Council elected the early adoption of Statement of Financial Accounting Standards ("SFAS") No. 117, *"Financial Statements of Not-for-Profit Organizations."* Under SFAS No. 117, the Council is required to report information regarding its financial position and activities according to three classes of net assets: unrestricted net assets; temporarily restricted net assets; and permanently restricted net assets. In addition, the Council is required to present a statement of cash flows. As permitted by this new statement, the Council has discontinued its use of fund accounting and has, accordingly, reclassified its financial statements to present the three classes of net assets required. This classification had no effect on the change in net assets for 1994.

Contributions

The Council also elected the early adoption of SFAS No. 116, *"Accounting for Contributions Received and Contributions Made,"* in 1994. In accordance with SFAS No. 116, grants and contracts received are recorded as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending on the existence and /or nature of any grantor restrictions. As permitted by SFAS No. 116, the Council has recognized the cumulative effect of the provisions of this new statement in its 1994 Statement of Activities. The adjustment of \$742,131 made to net assets as of June 30, 1994, represents time-restricted grants and contracts previously reported as deferred revenue. Under SFAS No. 116, such grants and contracts are required to be reported as temporarily restricted support and are then reclassified to unrestricted net assets upon expiration of the restriction. Assuming this new statement had been applied retroactively, the Council's change in net assets for 1994 would have been \$38,461, \$742,131 less than reported.

C Restrictions on Assets

Temporarily restricted net assets for 1995 and 1994 include \$845,556 and \$991,513, respectively, that is available for human resources development and \$233,333 and \$300,000, respectively, that is available for unrestricted general support.

D Income Taxes

The Council, a private operating foundation, is exempt from federal income tax under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

E Net Assets Released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors. The following is a summary of net assets released from grantor restrictions in 1995.

Purpose restrictions accomplished:	
Human resources	\$ 58,211
Leadership development	<u>87,746</u>
	145,957
Time restrictions expired	<u>416,667</u>
Total restrictions released	<u>\$ 562,624</u>

F Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council's contributions. The Council contributes 15% of employees' salaries to the Plan each year. The Council's contribution was \$50,544 and \$50,599 in fiscal years 1995 and 1994, respectively.

G Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents and grants receivable.

At June 30, 1995 and 1994, approximately \$182,048 and \$326,708, respectively, in cash equivalents was being held by a third party in a money market mutual fund that invests solely in United States government securities. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation.

Substantially all grants receivable are with large foundations. It is not the Council's policy to require collateral for these receivables. The Council has not incurred any losses in relation to these receivables.

H Commitments

The Council has entered into a noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in May, 1998. Under the terms of the lease agreement, the Council is required to pay its proportionate share of the increase in operating costs of the building.

Future minimum lease payments required under the lease are as follows:

Year Ending June 30:

1996	\$ 51,192
1997	51,192
1998	<u>46,926</u>
	<u>\$149,310</u>

I Affiliation

In February 1995, the Council agreed to affiliate with the Commission on Preservation and Access, Inc. (the "Commission") on the basis that both Organizations' missions and activities have become complementary as advances in technologies continue to create challenges and opportunities for libraries and other depositories of information. The Board of Directors for the Council and the Commission on Preservation and Access, Inc. agreed to the following principles of affiliation:

- The missions of each organization will remain distinct but complimentary;
- Independence and responsibility of each Board of Directors will be preserved;
- Each Organization will retain financial independence and responsibility;
- Cooperative projects may be undertaken when approved by each Organization's Board of Directors;
- Both Organizations will have a common President and Treasurer; and,
- The President is authorized and directed to implement such affiliation through any and all means deemed advisable, including, but not limited to, reorganizing the daily operations of each organization by consolidating employees and programmatic assignments.

J Related Party Transactions

As a result of the affiliation as described in Note I, the Council incurred charges of \$31,836 representing the Council's proportionate share of administrative expenses. As of June 30, 1995 \$12,218 was unpaid by the Commission to the Council.

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Functional Expenses

For the Year Ended June 30, 1995

(with Comparative Totals for the Year Ended June 30, 1994)

	Program Services				
	Human Resources	Access and Processing	Economics	Infra- structure	Total Program Services Expenses
Unrestricted:					
Grants	\$ -	\$ 9,840	\$ 52,090	\$ 24,880	\$ 86,810
Refunds and over appropriations	(29,895)	-	-	(5,816)	(35,711)
Staff and travel	98,527	21,752	25,706	61,709	207,694
Advisory committees, consultants, interns	21,180	3,764	9,522	43,952	78,418
Board expenses	-	-	-	-	-
Projects	46,465	-	-	-	46,465
Support services, incl. office expenses	<u>36,042</u>	<u>31,739</u>	<u>32,085</u>	<u>38,173</u>	<u>138,039</u>
	<u>\$ 172,319</u>	<u>\$ 67,095</u>	<u>\$ 119,403</u>	<u>\$ 162,898</u>	<u>\$ 521,715</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements

<u>Development</u>	<u>Administration</u>	<u>Total 1995</u>	<u>Total 1994</u>
\$ -	\$ -	\$ 86,810	\$ 223,469
-	-	(35,711)	(13,476)
24,754	191,520	423,968	458,718
3,430	4,204	86,052	120,360
-	16,986	16,986	35,591
-	-	46,465	-
<u>1,050</u>	<u>32,058</u>	<u>171,147</u>	<u>189,331</u>
<u>\$ 29,234</u>	<u>\$ 244,768</u>	<u>\$ 795,717</u>	<u>\$ 1,013,993</u>

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine...* (Paris, 1588). It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

Council on Library Resources

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